

Nonlinear Viscoelastic Behavior of Glassy Polymers and Its Effect on the Onset of Irreversible Deformation of the Matrix Resin in Continuous Fiber Composites

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SUMMARY

Predictions of a validated nonlinear viscoelastic model for glassy polymer will be presented for multiaxial deformations, where it will be shown that onset of yield can be described by a strain invariant criterion. Subsequently, the onset of irreversible deformation in off-axis tensile tests of unidirectional laminates of an epoxy-carbon fiber composite will be described using a strain invariant criterion.

Keywords: glassy polymers, nonlinear viscoelastic, strain invariants

INTRODUCTION

The off-axis tensile test has been utilized to examine the elastic and ultimate behavior of composite materials subjected to controlled states of multi-axial deformation in fiber-reinforced composite materials for the past forty years [1-2]. As the fiber angle is varied between 0 and $\pi/2$, the state of stress and strain within the composite material varies between states that are dominated by distortional and dilatational deformation. Moreover, the onset and ultimate states typically occur simultaneously in the off-axis tensile test. This coincidence enables a direct experimental determination of the onset of irreversible deformation and is in contrast to the general case for ultimate behavior wherein damage propagation must occur before onset can be detected. Consequently, the off-axis tensile test provides an excellent platform for evaluation of irreversible deformation in polymer matrix composites.

Conventional failure theories for composite materials focus on stress and strain states within the effective orthotropic medium and thereby ignore the fact that failure must occur in either of the two constituents and/or at the interface, not in an *aphysical* effective medium. Thus, one needs to address onset of failure through a more fundamental description of onset in the constituent materials. In the present paper, we describe the state-of-the-art in nonlinear viscoelastic (NLVE) constitutive modeling of glassy polymers. Next, the yield condition for this NLVE model will be analyzed for a range of multiaxial deformations in order to develop a strain-invariant onset criterion, which is then exercised to analyze experimental off-axis tensile test results for a graphite fiber – epoxy resin system for a range in off-axis angles from 10 to 90 degrees.

FUNDAMENTAL CONSTITUTIVE MODEL FOR GLASSY POLYMERS

Both thermoplastic and thermoset polymers in the glassy state exhibit nonlinear viscoelastic behavior, including temperature, pressure and strain rate dependent tensile/shear modulus [3], yield that depends upon both the thermal and deformation history [4], and complex volume relaxation as the material is cooled from above the glass transition temperature T_g into the glass [5]. A number of constitutive models have been proposed to describe the nonlinear viscoelastic response of glassy polymers, where most of these models employ a material time t^* defined as [6]

$$t^* = \int_0^t \frac{d\zeta}{a(\zeta)} \quad (1)$$

where $a(t)$ is a shift function that is a generalization of the well know a_T time-temperature shift function. The key physical postulate in these material time NLVE constitutive models is that the rate of viscoelastic relaxation can be accelerate/decelerated by deformation in addition to temperature. The difference between the various NLVE models is the functional dependence of $a(t)$, where free volume [7-9], stress [10], Adam-Gibbs configurational entropy [11] and configurational internal energy [12] have all been proposed. When the mobility depends upon stress alone, it is not possible to describe the nonlinear volume relaxation following a quench into the glass, because the isobaric stress is both constant and small. The free volume constitutive models are unable to describe multi-axial yield phenomena. Specifically, in uniaxial extension the free volume increase associated with deformation induced dilatation increases the mobility and induces yield, but in compression the material densifies thereby reducing the free volume; consequently, compression yield will not be predicted with a free volume model, which is not consistent with experiments. The only constitutive model to-date capable of unifying (i) volume relaxation and the associated thermal stress upon cooling into the glass, (ii) tension and compression yield and (iii) effects of physical aging on the yield is the NLVE configurational internal energy model of Caruthers et al. [12].

The Caruthers et al. [12] NLVE model that employs the configurational internal energy is an extension of an earlier constitutive model developed by Lustig et al. [13], where $a(t)$ can be a function of any thermodynamic variable (i.e. the stress, entropy, internal energy, etc.) that is determined self-consistently from a single non-equilibrium Helmholtz free energy functional. The NLVE model [12] (i) postulates that $\log a(t)$ is a function of the instantaneous configurational internal energy and (ii) employs a Hencky finite strain measure rather than the more traditional right Cauchy Green strain so that nearly incompressible behavior is predicted for large deformations at temperature well above T_g . This NLVE model is the simplest constitutive model that (i) is consistent with the basic requirements of continuum physics, (ii) employs an $a(t)$ shift function that depends upon the thermodynamic state of the material that is self-consistently determined from the underlying non-equilibrium Helmholtz potential and (iii) limits appropriately for a material well above T_g . Although there may be constitutive models for glassy polymers that are mathematically simpler than this NLVE constitutive model, they must have more complex physical assumptions. The NLVE constitutive model [12] for glassy polymer has been extensively validated at Sandia National Laboratory for both thermoset and thermoplastic materials [14].

The key challenge in developing a theory for onset of irreversible deformation of the matrix resin in composite materials is to determine the critical variable, when the

material transitions from a reversible elastic response to an irreversible viscoelastic response. In the t^* -based NLVE models described above, the onset of significant viscoelastic relaxation occurs when $a(t)$ is approximately equal to that of an undeformed material at T_g . Specifically, as the material is cooled from above T_g into the glass, $a(t)$ increases by orders-of-magnitude, where relaxation processes fall out of equilibrium at T_g ; and, when the glass is deformed, $a(t)$ is increased by the deformation. To a first approximation, at temperatures below T_g the shift factor $a(t)$ is greater than its value at T_g for an undeformed material and there is no viscoelastic relaxation; in contrast, when $a(t)$ is less than its value at T_g , viscoelastic relaxation occurs, where the decrease in $a(t)$ can be effected by temperature, deformation or a combination of temperature and deformation. In the constitutive model of Caruthers et al. [12] $\log a(t)$ depends upon the configurational internal energy e_c in a form that is similar to that initially postulated by Adam-Gibbs [11] for the configurational entropy; specifically,

$$\log a = C_1 \left(\frac{e_c^0}{e_c} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

where e_c^0 is the configurational internal energy in the reference state and C_1 is the WLF parameter. By definition configurational quantities include the contributions to the overall energy, entropy, etc. from rearrangement of the molecules, but do not include vibrational and electronic contribution to the various thermodynamic quantities. For the situation where a material is cooled deep into the glass and then deformed, the configurational internal energy during deformation prior to the point that significant deformation induced viscoelastic relaxation occurs is given by

$$\begin{aligned} e_c(T, V, t_f, t'_f) = & e_c^0 + V_{ref} \Delta G I_D - 2 \Delta A T \int_{t'_f}^{t_f} a_\Delta(t^* - \xi^*, 0) \frac{dI_V}{d\xi} d\xi \\ & - 2 \Delta C T \int_{t'_f}^{t_f} c_\Delta(t^* - \xi^*, 0) \frac{dT}{d\xi} d\xi + \text{double integral terms} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where e_c^0 is the configurational internal energy of an undeformed material at T_g and reference volume $V_{ref} = V_{equil}(p=1\text{atm}, T_g)$, T is the temperature, and the material properties ΔG , ΔA and ΔC are respectively the difference between the *linear* glassy and rubber shear modulus, thermal stress and heat capacity. The dilatational (i.e. volume) invariant I_V and the deviatoric invariant I_D are given by

$$I_V = \text{tr}(\mathbf{H}) = \ln \left(\frac{V}{V_{ref}} \right) \quad I_D = \left(\mathbf{H} : \mathbf{H} - \frac{1}{3} I_V^2 \right) \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{H} = 1/2 \ln \mathbf{C}$ is the Hencky deformation tensor, and \mathbf{C} is the right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor. The reference configuration for \mathbf{H} is the undeformed equilibrium material at T_g at atmospheric pressure. Examining Eqn. 3, the single and double integral terms are constants, although the values of these constants depend upon the thermal/deformation history that was used to form the glass. Thus, e_c , and hence the mobility that results in onset, only depends upon the deviatoric strain invariant. Once I_D and thus e_c and $a(t)$ are such that deformation induced viscoelastic relaxation begins, the full expression for e_c , must be used rather than the simple form of e_c , given in Eqn. 3.

PREDICTIONS OF THE NLVE CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

The polymer matrix in a fiber reinforced composite experiences a complex, multi-axial deformation history even when the deformation history applied to the composite is simple. One could of course employ a micromechanics simulation using the full nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive model; however, the computational effort of performing this detailed FEA simulation for all deformation histories is substantial. As an alternative, in this Section we will examine the predictions of the NLVE constitutive model [12] for a suite of representative deformation histories to determine if a relatively simple onset criterion can be developed.

Figure 1 Schematic of deformation with differing amounts of dilatation and shear. There is no deformation in the z direction

In the composite the matrix resin will experience a range of deformation conditions that range from shear to dilation. Consider the deformation geometry shown schematically in Fig. 1, where the polymer matrix is in a thin slit of thickness H between two rigid fixtures that are deformed in the x -direction. If the slit is very thin, the sample cannot deform in the y' - and z' -directions; thus, the deformation is statically determinate, depending only upon the strain in the axial direction ϵ defined as u/H . The right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor for this deformation geometry is

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} (1 + \epsilon S)^2 & \epsilon C(1 + \epsilon S) & 0 \\ \epsilon C(1 + \epsilon S) & 1 + \epsilon^2 C^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $S = \sin\theta$ and $C = \cos\theta$. When θ is 0° , this is a shear deformation and when θ is 90° there is a significant dilatational component to the deformation. The NLVE model [12] has been solved for the deformation defined by Eqn. 5 for a prototypical glassy material as specified in [15]. Since the objective is to determine the form of the criterion for onset of irreversible deformation, the exact details of the material properties are not critical as long as the properties are representative of a glass, although obviously the exact values of the critical criterion will of course depend upon the specific matrix material under consideration. The material is cooled at $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ isobarically at 1 atmosphere, where the contraction is isotropic, from well above T_g to $T_g - 40^\circ\text{C}$. A constant axial strain rate of $1.67 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ is applied. The xx , yy and xy components of the stress for uniaxial extension are shown in Fig. 2. A definite yield stress is predicted for σ_{xx} for angles from $\theta = 10^\circ$ to 90° , where the σ_{yy} component of the stress exhibits similar behavior as σ_{xx} . The σ_{xy} component of the stress tensor also exhibits a very definite yield point for all angles between 0° and 80° .

Figure 2 Stress-strain curves for geometry given in Fig. 3 for values of θ from 0° to 90° at 10° increments. Stress strain curves for σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and σ_{xy} at 90° are essentially zero.

For $\theta = 90^\circ$ there is no shear component to the stress tensor. The yield stress for σ_{xx} , σ_{xy} and σ_{yy} as a function of angle θ is shown in Fig. 3. A sharp post-yield softening is predicted for both σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} when $\theta \geq 40^\circ$. In contrast post-yield softening for the shear deformation (i.e. $\theta = 0^\circ$) is much less noticeable, which is a known limitation of the NLVE constitutive model. The values of the strain invariants at yield are shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 3 (Left) Yield stress for deformation geometry given in Fig. 3. σ_{xx} – circles; σ_{yy} – triangles and σ_{xy} – squares.

Figure 4 (Right) Strain invariants at yield for deformation geometry given in Fig. 3. J_1 – open markers; J_2' – filled markers.

For comparison with the results of [16] a slightly different notation is useful. The invariant

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \quad (6)$$

describes the dilatational component of the deformation, while the J_2' invariant defined by

$$J_2' = \sqrt{\frac{1}{6} \left[(\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2)^2 + (\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_3)^2 + (\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_3)^2 \right]} \quad (7)$$

describes the shape changing part of the deformation, where J_1 and J_2' are defined in terms of the principal strains of the Green-Lagrange strain measure $\mathbf{E}=1/2(\mathbf{C}-\mathbf{I})$. The relationship between the invariants of the Hencky strain tensor I_V and I_D and the invariants J_1 and J_2' is

$$J_1 \approx I_V \quad \text{and} \quad J_2' \approx \sqrt{I_D/2} \quad (8)$$

where the approximate equalities in Eqn. 8 are exact for small deformations. J_1 dominates when $\theta = 0^\circ$, while J_2' dominates when $\theta = 90^\circ$. The yield condition in J_1 - J_2' space is given in Fig. 5. The yield surface is slightly different if determined from the maximum in the σ_{xx} or σ_{yy} versus the σ_{xy} components of the strain; however, the shape of the yield surface is identical. This difference is because the relaxation response in σ_{xy} component in the stress tensor has a stronger influence from the shear modulus $G(t) = \Delta G \cdot g_\Delta(t)$ vs. the bulk modulus $K(t) = \Delta K \cdot k_\Delta(t)$ and the thermal stress $A(t) = \Delta A \cdot a_\Delta(t)$ terms that are more important for the σ_{xx} or σ_{yy} components. When J_1 is less than 0.015, there is an upturn in the yield surface, which is due to the lack of a definite yield point for a sample in a shear deformation as shown in Fig. 2. When J_1 is greater than 0.015 the yield conditions merge into a critical value of J_2' that is independent of J_1 and insensitive to the temperature and strain rate. Thus, to first order the NLVE viscoelastic constitutive model [12] predicts that yield, or the irreversible flow that precedes the yield point, occurs when J_2' reaches a critical value.

The yield surface predictions shown in Fig. 5 are for the spatially homogeneous deformations illustrated in Fig. 1. For the case of uniform triaxial extension (i.e. $J_2'=0$) the NLVE constitutive model predicts that the material could infinitely expand without any yield; however, at some point an instability will occur, a local shear component will develop and the material will exhibit a deviatoric driven yield. The determination of the critical value of J_1 at which the instability develops requires a stability analysis of the FEA solution of the NLVE constitutive model with the appropriate conservation equations. This FEA analysis is beyond the scope of this paper. However, we know that there will be a critical J_1 at which the onset of irreversible behavior as well as yield will occur.

The key conclusion is that the onset of irreversible deformation in glassy polymers is given by a surface in the space of *strain invariants* J_1 and J_2' . In contrast, an onset theory that is based upon stress invariants will be unsuccessful, because the stress at yield, and similarly at onset, significantly changes with type of deformation (see Fig. 2, where the yield stress changes by a factor 3 as θ goes from 0° to 90°) as well as with temperature and strain rate. The remainder of this communication

Figure 5 Yield surface predicted by thermo-viscoelastic model for material defined in text. Filled squares – $T=T_g - 40^\circ\text{C}$, strain rate $1.67 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$; open squares – $T=T_g - 50^\circ\text{C}$, strain rate $1.67 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$; triangles – $T=T_g - 40^\circ\text{C}$, strain rate $1.67 \times 10^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$.

will demonstrate how strain invariant criteria for onset of flow in the matrix can be used to predict onset of failure in polymer matrix composites.

OFF-AXIS TENSION TEST AND COMPOSITE ONSET CRITERION

The experimental results of off-axis tensile tests of a commercial graphite fiber in epoxy matrix resin (IM7/977-3 from Cytec Engineered Materials Inc[®]) are reported in a companion paper in the ICCM17 conference by Gosse and Pipes. Briefly, test coupons with a 152.4 mm gauge length and 19.05 mm were produced from a unidirectional laminate panel. Test conditions were room temperature with ambient pressure and humidity and all testing was conducted at a displacement rate of 1.27 mm/min. Results for each coupon test configuration involved ten replicates, where the peak value in each data set was chosen to determine the onset of irreversible behavior. The fiber orientations between 10° and 90° were investigated, where the specimen geometry was such that at 10° no fiber was supported by both grips.

Gosse and Pipes in the companion paper determined the macroscopic deformation field in the composite coupon as the point of failure, using FEA of anisotropic materials. The location of the maximum deformation is located between the fiber axis that passes through the centroid of the coupon and the grip. The deformation at this point is then used as the boundary conditions in a FEA micromechanics simulation. The micromechanics simulation uses a representative volume element of a fiber in the matrix, where the fiber is either cubically or hexagonally packed and both the fiber and matrix are assumed to be linear thermoelastic materials with their room temperature values of material properties. The deformation field of the matrix inside of the composite depends upon both (i) the local elastic thermal stresses as the material is cooled from T_g to room temperature and (ii) the externally applied deformation field determined from macroscopic FEA analysis. The local deformation field in the matrix is micromechanically enhanced as compared to the external deformation field [16]. The deformation field in the matrix is interrogated at several predetermined locations in the matrix resin and J_1 and J_2' invariants determined at these points.

Using the analysis of Gosse and Pipes described above, the strain invariants at the point of failure are determined. Since onset of irreversible deformation and failure are coincident for off-axis tests of unidirectional laminate, these are the invariants at onset for this particular resin system. In a similar manner to the NLVE analysis of yield in polymeric resins as described in the previous section, the maximum $J_1 - J_2'$ points in the resin at onset (i.e. the off-axis point of failure) are shown in Fig. 6 for the various fiber orientations. For fiber angles of 10, 15 and 20 degrees in the off-axis laminate failure occurs at a critical value of the deviatoric strain invariant of approximately 0.11, while for fiber angles of 25, 30, 45, 67 and 90 degrees failure occurs at a critical value of the isotropic invariant of 0.024. The data clearly indicates the validity of a strain invariant onset criterion is consistent with the form suggested by the NLVE constitutive model [12]. It should be noted that this relatively simple strain invariant onset criteria is only possible by considering the local deformation field in the polymer matrix, which has been micromechanically enhanced by the presence of the fibers in a complex manner that depends upon (i) fiber orientation, volume fraction and packing geometry, (ii) elastic properties of the polymer matrix and carbon fibers, (iii) thermal stresses that

occur during manufacture of the composite material and (iv) the externally applied deformation field. We believe that the results shown in Fig. 6 provide the first steps toward a rational onset theory for polymer matrix continuous fiber composites.

Figure 6 J_2' versus J_1 for off-axis tensile testing of unidirectional IM7/977-3 composites

CONCLUSION

The onset of irreversible deformation in the polymeric matrix of an off-axis tensile test for a carbon fiber composite was examined by using the strain invariant criterion. A non-linear viscoelastic model for a glassy polymer was examined and it was found that a unique value of J_2' does coincide with onset of yield in the polymer. Further, the key conclusion in this work is that the onset of irreversible deformation in glassy polymers is given by a surface in the space of *strain invariants* J_1 and J_2' . In contrast, an onset theory that is based upon stress invariants will be unsuccessful, because the stress at yield, and similarly at onset, significantly changes with type of deformation.

Micromechanical analysis of off-axis tensile experiments on unidirectional laminates of a graphite fiber in an epoxy resin system [16] was used to determine the values of the J_1 and J_2' strain invariants at the point of failure. Since onset of irreversible deformation and ultimate failure are coincident for these experiments, the values of these invariants correspond to the onset of irreversible deformation. The off-axis data show a very simple onset criteria, where onset is observed if either J_1 or J_2' exceeds a critical value. For more general composite configurations, i.e. not unidirectional laminates, onset is typically followed by propagation of damage, where prediction of onset is clearly only the first step in treating this more general problem. However, for design approaches where onset of irreversible behavior is the guiding design principle, the present approach should be adequate.

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References

1. Pipes RB, Cole BW. On the Off-Axis Strength Test for Anisotropic Materials. *J Compos Mater* 1973;7:246-256.
2. Pindera MJ, Herakovich, CT. Shear Characterization of Unidirectional Composites with the Off-Axis Tension Test. *Exp Mech* 1986;26(1):103-112.
3. Schapery RA. Nonlinear Viscoelastic Solids. *Int J Solids Struct* 2000;37(1-2):359-366.
4. Haward RN. *The Physics of Glassy Polymers*. London: Applied Science Publishers LTD, 1973.
5. Kovacs AJ. (1963), Transition Vitreuse dans les Polymeres Amorphes. Etude Phenomenologique. *Fortschr Hochpolym Forsch* 1963;3:394-507.
6. Hopkins IL. Stress Relaxation or Creep of Linear Viscoelastic Substances under Varying Temperature. *J Polym Sci* 1958;28(118):631-633.
7. Knauss WG, Emri IJ. Non-Linear Viscoelasticity Based on Free-Volume Consideration. *Comput Struct* 1981;13(1-3):123-128.
8. Knauss WG, Emri IJ. Volume Change and the Nonlinearly Thermoviscoelastic Constitution of Polymers. *Polym Eng Sci* 1987;27(1):86-100.
9. Losi GU, Knauss WG. Free-Volume Theory and Nonlinear Thermoviscoelasticity. *Polym Eng Sci* 1992;32(8):542-557.
10. Schapery RA. On Characterization of Nonlinear Viscoelastic Materials. *Polym Eng Sci* 1969;9(4):295-310.
11. Adam G, Gibbs JH. On Temperature Dependence of Cooperative Relaxation Properties in Glass-Forming Liquids. *J Chem Phys* 1965;43(1):139-146.
12. Caruthers JM, Adolf DB, Chambers RS, Shrikhande P. A thermodynamically consistent, nonlinear viscoelastic approach for modeling glassy polymers. *Polymer* 2004;45(13):4577-4597.
13. Lustig SR, Shay RM, Caruthers JM. Thermodynamic constitutive equations for materials with memory on a material time scale. *J Rheol* 1996;40(1):69-106.
14. Adolf DB, Chambers RS, Caruthers JM. Extensive Validation of a Thermodynamically Consistent, Nonlinear Viscoelastic Model for Glassy Polymers. *Polymer* 2004;45(13):4599-4621.
15. Martin RA. Investigation of Linear and Nonlinear Viscoelastic Behavior of Polymethylmethacrylate. MS. Thesis, Purdue University, School of Chemical Engineering, 2007.
16. Buchanan DL, Gosse JH, Wollschlager JA, Ritchey A, Pipes RB. Micromechanical Enhancement of the Macroscopic Strain State for Advanced Composite Materials. submitted to *Composites Science and Technology*, 2009.